

Silicon-Based Lithium-Ion Battery Cell Material Tests, Supported by Finite-Element Model Simulations

Florian Feyersinger¹, Philip Kargl¹(✉), Johannes Aegerter², Loic Dehottay³,
Thomas Devahif³, Alexander Thaler¹, and Medina Custic¹

¹ Virtual Vehicle Research GMBH, 8010 Graz, Austria
{florian.feyersinger, philip.kargl}@v2c2.at

² Speira GMBH, Georg-von-Boeselager-Str. 21, 53117 Bonn, Germany

³ Circuit Foil, Salzbaach 6, 9559 Wiltz, Luxembourg

<https://www.virtual-vehicle.at/>, <https://greenspeed-project.eu/>

Abstract. The greenSPEED projects ambition is to create a safe, long-lived, high-capacity battery cell, while reducing the carbon footprint and environmental impact during its production. This will open the opportunity for cheaper and “greener” mobile electric applications.

Focusing on the development of a new generation of lithium (Li) ion battery cells, containing specially treated copper and aluminium foils as current collectors and promising silicon-based anode material. Tests are carried out on pouch cells and cylindrical cells (21700) and are supported by finite element model (FEM) simulations

Tensile tests are done for the different cell components to obtain material parameters for FEM simulations. The specific material models will be used to assemble a cell model to propose improvements for cell design and the overall mechanical properties of the cell.

The newly developed battery cells will additionally be tested for their expansion behaviour under varying conditions and the data will be used to parameterise an expansion model which will be used for the cell simulations. The combination of material specific models and expansion model will lead to simulations which give insight in the mechanical behaviour of the battery cell and stress distribution during charge and discharge. This toolchain will increase the development speed and provides a modular framework for further investigations.

Keywords: Battery · FEM · Silicon · Simulation · Lithium Ion
Battery · Copper Foil · Aluminium Foil

1 Introduction

Battery production nowadays is demanding very high energy densities as well as safe and environmentally friendly production which are both non trivial restrictions. The search for the right material is often limited by the experience with

and availability of products. A component that is often neglected is the current collector foil for both electrodes. Copper (Cu) as the dominant choice for the anode current collector foil and Aluminum (Al) as the preferred choice as cathode current collector foil can both be prepared in various ways spanning different pre-coatings, thicknesses, temperatures and other surface treatments.

Silicon in its pure form has an extremely attractive theoretical capacity of about 4200 mAh/g [1]. Its impact on Li-ion battery industry, so far, was nevertheless negligible. One of the main reasons for that is the drastic expansion, about 300% [2], of silicon while intercalating Li, which introduces mechanical stress in the cell, leading to crumbling of the electrode and therefore to moderate cycle stability in Li-ion battery cells. The expansion can be reduced by using silicon-based compounds while also reducing the capacity of the material compared to pure silicon. The right choice in current collector, however, will improve cycle stability without negative impact on capacity.

In this work, we focus on specially treated foils for this specific battery cell generation, using a pure silicon anode.

The material characterisation is important for the follow up simulations for single cells and cell design. Especially, the predicted behaviour of the anode for the upcoming cylindrical cell production is of importance.

State of the art material tests are used and measurement standards for Cu and Al foils have been tested. The production supporting FEM simulations are done in commercially available finite element solver LS-DYNA [4]. The mechanical cell model in addition includes an electrical model using Randles elements [3] (EM_RANDLES_SOLID) as well as a recently added state of charge dependent expansion model MAT_ADD_SOC_EXPANSION_TITLE.

2 Material and Battery Tests

An example of a stress-strain curve obtained from a tensile test is given in Fig. 1, this test was carried out on Al foil sample as it can be used in lithium ion batteries as cathode current collector. A set of parameters, from now on called material model, can be extracted from this experiment including yield strength, elasticity modulus and plastic load curve. Yield strength and elasticity modulus can be obtained by applying the 0.2% offset rule [6]. The tests are repeated at least 3 times to allow statistic evaluation of the material parameters. The pure Si anode changes its volume during insertion and extraction of Li-ions. This behaviour is crucial for further cell design. Therefore, experimental data is needed to have appropriate theoretical expansion models. The cell expansion can be measured during formation as well as constant current/constant voltage cycling, which will also provide cell performance information needed to setup the electrical simulation. The used experimental setup is described in detail in the paper of Kargl et al. [7] We apply a pressure of 0.5MPa during the experiment and can relate cell expansion to the SOC (State of Charge) of the battery. This experiment has been done with 3 cells to obtain an average cell behaviour.

Fig. 1. Example stress σ versus strain result for Al. engineering values in blue, true stress and strain in dashed orange, 0.2% offset method line in dashed red with results in dashed black, yield point as black rhombus. Source: Authors

3 Battery and Material Models

The main impact on the cell predictions, outside of the material model, will be given by the definition of simulation parameters and key influences on the cell, as defined as follows. In this paper we apply a constant current profile on Randles elements defined by experimentally obtained parameters. The current profile charges the cell from 20% to 80% SOC at a constant current. Furthermore, expansion of the anode is included, since Si is known to expand up to 300% while intercalating Li.

The material model for each experiment is optimized with LS-OPT [5] to obtain a better match with experimental data, including simulation approximations. An example for comparison of the extracted material model and the optimized material model to the corresponding measurement is given in Fig. 2. Due to the simplifications in our model and the extraction method, the experimentally obtained values do not automatically match the simulation results. The initial material model is not able to reproduce the experimental data well in our simulations, whereas a good agreement is reached after a few optimization iterations. The optimized parameters for each material are used to create an average material model which will be used in the simulations. The parameterised cell component models are assembled to a bi-layer cell model which is used for the simulations. The stack of the pouch cell includes separators at the top and bottom as well as between the cathode and anodes (two single-side coated anodes and a double-side coated cathode in the centre). Each electrode has an extension of the current collector to allow electrical contact, called tab. A pouch foil envelops the stack and is sealed on the edges while allowing cathode tab and anode tab to stick out. Due to the layout of the pouch cell, two Randle elements are included in the cell, representing the two “layers” of the bi-layer cell, with each “layer” corresponding to one anode active material side and one cathode active material side. The thickness change of the silicon anode is much higher

Fig. 2. Simulation data with experimentally extracted model (red), optimized simulation data (purple) and experimental data (dashed blue). Source: Authors

compared to the cathode, which is why the cathode contribution is neglected in the model. This allows to obtain the anode-expansion introduced stress from simulation, an important parameter for cell design and development.

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 3 shows the resulting displacement as response to the anode expansion. One can see that the pouch foil in this case is lifted together with the underlying stack, which is the result for the induced stress seen in Fig. 4. The electrode tabs are mainly displaced close to the main stack body. This is true for all tabs that are above the very first anode, since the anode is responsible for expansion in this cell. The second anode tab, which is located close to the top of the stack, is

Fig. 3. Simulation results of the displacement of mesh nodes, left: the full pouch cell and right: the stack inside the pouch cell. This figure was created using LS-PrePost. Source: Authors

displaced due to expansion and forces the first anode tab, close to the bottom of the stack, also to be displaced since they are connected to each other. In other words the second anode tab is slowly pushed away from the first.

Also the cathode tab, here a single one shown to the right of the pouch cell, is displaced close to the stack due to anode expansion, which might become a problem since the pouch foil covering the tabs will fixate the tabs.

Fig. 4. Simulation results of the stress distribution inside left: full bi-layer pouch cell and right: stack inside the pouch cell. This figure was created using LS-PrePost. Source: Authors

These effects might lead to failure if the pouch swells further or for multi-layer pouch cells, which would lead to higher absolute expansion. Figure 4 shows the stress distribution inside the pouch cell. While the pouch foil itself is not affected too much by anode expansion, we can see that the stress increases in the cell stack as well as on the tabs. The connected anode tab shows maximum stress on the interface between the two tabs since they are pushed apart, whereas the single cathode tab exhibits the highest stress close to the stack.

Overall, we present an approach of battery cell simulations, starting from simple material analysis resulting in a coupled electro-mechanical FEM of a bi-layer pouch cell. The obtained data can be used for defining regions of interest in cell design as well as areas of potential failure in extensive cell use and up-scaling.

In future simulations, this approach will also be used for 21700 cells. The combination of Si anodes in 21700 cells will need support on simulation side to get insight in the pressure and stress distribution inside the cell which is not feasible experimentally as well as locations of possible areas of failure/interest. As one example, the jelly roll in cylindrical cells is assembled by a rolling process. During this step, considerable stresses are introduced in the jelly roll which can be analysed using an adapted version of the presented mechanical model. In a subsequent step, the anode expansion can be simulated to further investigate expansion-induced stresses and will lead to a better understanding of design limitations.

Acknowledgement. The publication was written at Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH in Graz and partially funded within the COMET K2 Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies from the Austrian Federal Ministry for Climate Action (BMK), the Austrian Federal Ministry for Labour and Economy (BMAW), the Province of Styria (Dept. 12) and the Styrian Business Promotion Agency (SFG). The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) has been authorised for the programme management.

Funded by the European Union (GA: 101069528). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

1. Chan, C., Peng, H., Liu, G., et al.: High-performance lithium battery anodes using silicon nanowires. *Nat. Nanotech.* **3**, 31–35 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2007.411>
2. Graetz, J., et al.: Highly reversible lithium storage in nanostructured silicon. *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.* **6**, A194 (2003). <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1596917>
3. L'Eplattenier, P., et al.: A distributed randle circuit model for battery abuse simulations using LS-DYNA. In: 2016 14th International LS-DYNA Users Conference (2016)
4. LS-DYNA, Livermore Software Technology Corporation
5. LS-OPT, Livermore Software Technology Corporation
6. Christensen, R.M.: *The Theory of Materials Failure*. OUP Oxford, United Kingdom (2013)
7. Kargl, P., et al.: Investigation of voltage and expansion hysteresis of Si-alloy-C/NMC622 pouch cells using dilatometry. *J. Power Sources* **548**, 232042 (2022)

Open Access This chapter is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license and indicate if changes were made.

The images or other third party material in this chapter are included in the chapter's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the chapter's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder.

